

Spectral Investigations of the Structure of the Complex Compound formed between Cobalt (II) and Chloride Ions in Aqueous Solutions (I)

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The temperature dependence of the absorption spectra of CoCl_4^{2-} in aqueous solution in visible region has been investigated between the temperatures 25° to 70° .

There is no detailed literature data regarding the investigations of the temperature dependence of the complex formed between Co^{++} and Cl^- in the aqueous solutions. Some work in this field was carried out by Andreev and Khaldin¹.

Previously many workers² have studied the structure of the complex formed between Co^{++} and Cl^- in aqueous solution. In our laboratories we studied the formation of the complex in strong MgCl_2 solutions. It was observed during the course of experiments that a small change in the temperature leads to a considerable change in the intensity of the absorption band. It was also observed that at room temperature in aqueous solution the minimum chloride ion concentration required to form appreciable quantity of complex with cobalt was about 7 mole/lit. Whereas at the high temperature of about 60° appreciable quantity of the complex was formed at as low as 4 mole/lit. of chloride ion.

All the spectra were taken on the Russian recording spectrophotometer 'CФ-10'.

For obtaining different constant temperatures for the solutions under investigation a special double wall cell holder was made of lead through which water at constant temperature was circulated from an ultrathermostat. The temperature was measured directly by a thermometer placed inside the cell containing the solution at the time when absorption peak was recorded.

Following solutions were prepared :

Solution No. 1

0.1 mol/lit. of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 5.0 mol/lit. of KCl.

Solution No. 2

0.1 mol/lit. of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 4.5 mol/lit. of KCl.

Solution No. 3

0.1 mole/lit. of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 4.0 mol/lit. of KCl.

1. S. N. Andreev and V. G. Khaldin, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1962, **32**, 3845-52.
2. Cotton et. al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4690,

Spectra of all the three solutions were taken at different temperatures and are recorded in Figs. 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Optical density of all the solutions at different temperatures is given in the following table.

TABLE

Solution No. 1			Solution No. 2			Solution No. 3		
Spect. No.	Temperature °C	Optical Density with 1 cm. path length at $\lambda = 700 \text{ m}\mu$	Spect. No.	Temperature °C	Optical Density with 1 cm. path length at $\lambda = 700 \text{ m}\mu$	Spect. No.	Temperature °C	Optical Density with 1 cm. path length at $\lambda = 700 \text{ m}\mu$
1	75	1.79	1	70	1.02	1	75.0	0.67
2	73	1.69	2	66	0.70	2	70.5	0.52
3	69	1.38	3	63	0.59	3	66.0	0.38
4	68	1.29	4	60	0.53	4	61.0	0.27
5	64	0.90	5	58	0.42	5	51.0	0.17
6	62	0.86	6	55	0.34	6	42.0	0.13
7	60	0.71	7	51	0.25	7	27.0	0.09
8	55	0.59	8	39	0.12			
9	50	0.37	9	25	0.10			
10	40	0.21						
11	26	0.09						

For the above three solutions, at 100m temperature absorption bands are observed only in the region $420 \text{ m}\mu$ to $580 \text{ m}\mu$. With main maxima at approximately $515 \text{ m}\mu$ rise in temperature leads to the shift of this maxima towards high wavelength direction. At the same time there is observed an increase in the intensity of the total absorption bands.

Rise in temperature gives rise to another absorption band in the region between 600 $m\mu$ to 750 $m\mu$. Intensity of this band increases with the rise in temperature, but the form of the band remains the same as at room temperature with high chloride ion concentrations².

From the above observations following equilibrium can be concluded between Co^{+2} and Cl^- and the complex.

At room temperature in aqueous solutions cobalt ion exists as $Co(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ ^{1,3}. In the presence of chloride ion in solution it combines with the latter at high temperature. Reaction taking place at high temperature is concluded to be

From the expression 2 it can be said that the ΔH_1 for the formation of $Co(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ is more than ΔH_2 for the formation of $CoCl_4^{2-}$ and it agrees with the conclusion³ that for

$\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ ion Δ_1 of splitting of molecular orbital formed by hydrated cobalt ion is approximately three times more than the Δ_2 of CoCl_4^{2-} ($\Delta_1 = 9300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Delta_2 = 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

As such this may be taken as the reason for the observation that only at very high concentration of Cl^- in aqueous solution CoCl_4^{2-} complex is formed.

Further the absorption peak initially observed at $515 \text{ m}\mu$ —

a) shifts to higher wavelength and higher optical density with increasing chloride ion concentration.

b) has a considerably higher rate of increase of optical density with temperature in presence of chloride ions as compared with $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions of similar strength without chloride added (Fig. 4)

c) on increasing the chloride ion concentrations ultimately merges with the very much more prominent main absorption peak of CoCl_4^{2-} tetrahedral and becomes a hump on its absorption band.

It is certain that this peak is a mixed peak having contributions from (1) $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{++}$ and CoCl_4^{2-} tetrahedral, the latter becoming more prominent at higher chloride ion concentration and/or at higher temperatures.

However, this behaviour is not sufficient to rule out the formation of small quantities of an intermediate with greater extinction coefficient than hydrated cobalt ion. We also note here that cobalt in gaseous state has very strong absorption at $545 \text{ m}\mu$ which is the value towards which our peak is shifting. In solutions having very high KCl or MgCl_2 concentrations (near saturation) and thereby having effectively less of free water the existence of such an ion for short duration of time is not impossible.

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3. Harry B. Gray, "Electrons and Chemical Bond. Benjamin", New York, 1965.